

Four Axes Driving Research on Sustainable ICT: Impacts Assessment, Efficiency, Sufficiency and Resilience

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Introduction

We are currently experiencing a serious environmental and climate crisis of proven anthropogenic origin [IPCC 2021]. We live in a finite world with limited resources in minerals, metals, water, land area, non-renewable resources, etc. This finite world relies on fragile equilibrium states, including biodiversity, which are severely threatened. In this context of environmental and climate crisis, objectives were set by the Paris Agreement, ratified in 2015. These objectives aim to limit global warming to 2°C above pre-industrial temperatures. We are currently deviating from the paths that would allow us to meet these objectives. One universal objective, however, prevails: to guarantee a decent and equitable standard of living.

In this environmental crisis, all industrial sectors are affected: all must reduce their impacts, and ICT is no exception. ICT is often presented as part of the solution to climate problems. Indeed, it allows for the optimisation of data transfers, storage, and calculations; the detailed modelling of complex system interactions; the simulation of large-scale problems with a very large number of parameters; and the calculation of trajectories and prospective scenarios. However, ICT is undeniably part of the climate problem, both through its direct and indirect effects [Freitag 2021]. Direct effects concern the resources used throughout the life cycle of ICT devices: embodied energy, water, metals, etc. Indirect effects include optimisation, induction, obsolescence, acceleration, social transformation, and rebound effects [Horner

2016]. In recent years, numerous research studies have been launched towards green ICT or sustainable ICT. In the following, we classify them into four complementary, and often intertwined, research axes. In particular, these axes are explored in the context of a French research and service network named EcoInfo [EcoInfo].

Impacts assessment

More and more studies are focusing on environmental impact assessment, meaning assessment methods for direct and indirect impacts, whether positive or negative, and on the development of indicators and methodologies for allocating these impacts. One can, for instance, cite the GHG protocol for assessing greenhouse gas emissions [GHG Protocol].

The impacts can be numerous and diverse: energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, water consumption, use of mineral resources, pollution, rebound effects, efficiency gains, conflicts of use, etc. This research axis notably covers issues related to energy consumption and carbon footprint in order to: understand the information conveyed by indicators, measure them on various IT equipment using software and hardware power meters, design attribution models for these indicators for digital services and shared digital infrastructures, and develop simulation tools to evaluate these indicators at a large scale for given digital applications. Research targeting other environmental and societal indicators, whether single-criterion or multi-criteria, remains less explored, as does research focusing on the non-use phases of the

life cycle (end of life, for example, and electronic waste management), and research concerning indirect effects (obsolescence effects, direct and indirect rebound effects, systemic transformations) [Horner 2016].

Several methods exist for qualitatively or quantitatively estimating environmental and societal impacts. These methods either create a snapshot at a given moment (carbon footprint, material footprint, or attributional life cycle analysis), or answer questions about specific changes by identifying the difference with/without the targeted change (quantification of greenhouse gas emissions, project footprint, consequential life cycle analysis).

Currently, the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions of the digital sector are still the subject of debate regarding their quantification, but also regarding their trend (more or less pronounced increase). Research in this area is still recent and must nevertheless urgently address practical questions concerning the qualitative and quantitative assessment of impacts: of ICT on other sectors and other scientific disciplines, of the digitisation of services, of the introduction of new information technologies, and of research on ICT itself.

Efficiency

For several decades now, ICT research has also focused on efficiency, that is, achieving the same level of use with a reduced impact, optimising systems, and developing eco-design and reparability approaches to reduce resource waste. Efficiency concerns the optimisation of systems according to one or more criteria (resource consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, etc.). Efficiency issues concern both hardware and software aspects and their co-optimisation.

Historically, efficiency in terms of performance (e.g., computation time, memory space, silicon area, spectral efficiency) has been a concern since the start of ICT. However, except in some

specific areas such as embedded systems, the targeted criterion was primarily economic and not environmental or societal. Increasingly, research is focusing on energy efficiency in various areas of computing: hardware architectures, programming languages, compilation, data lifecycle, algorithms, optimisation techniques, communication network management, distributed systems, computing and storage infrastructures, etc. Some research studies go beyond the use phase and beyond energy and carbon criteria by exploring, for instance, the efficient use of water throughout the entire lifecycle, or by reducing the use of some abiotic resources.

This research axis encompasses efficient approaches (during the use phase) and eco-design (upstream during the design phase) for both software and hardware, as well as research related to multi-criteria trade-offs between performance and environmental impacts.

Eco-design can aim, in particular, to extend the lifespan of digital equipment, increase its reparability, fight against software and hardware obsolescence, or make infrastructures and systems adaptable to dynamically adjust resource use to user needs.

Research in this area may focus on optimising existing systems or developing new technologies. Regarding the optimisation of existing systems, numerous techniques are being explored, such as standby modes, dynamic adaptation of voltage, frequency, or radio channel, data compression, heterogeneous architectures, approximate computing, etc.

Efficiency can also be achieved by optimising the carbon footprint of the electricity used by harnessing renewable energy sources, which are often intermittent, variable over time, and difficult to predict (e.g., wind power). This axis is gradually leading to questions about the role of ICT in the energy transition as a sector on its own (part of the problem), and not simply as a tool that may contribute to this transition (part of the solution).

Sufficiency

More recently, research studies have shifted towards sufficiency or sobriety, meaning redefining uses and reorienting needs in relation to global challenges. Sobriety is often associated with notions of frugality, absolute environmental sustainability, or sufficiency, and raises the question of needs in relation to that of planetary boundaries [Rockström 2009]. Who can define these needs? How can we guarantee a reduction in inequalities and the social justice that is necessary for self-limitation? How can we design a 'low-tech' ICT, or one limited by design? What should these limits be?

Some research studies in ICT are beginning to address these boundary issues by proposing, for example, to adapt existing systems, software, or algorithms to take into account predetermined budgets, whether in terms of energy consumption (energy budget), greenhouse gas emissions (carbon quota), or usage time. These restrictive budgets imply changes in users' habits. The challenges are therefore multifaceted: determining technically achievable limits (from both a theoretical and practical point of view), proposing adaptable mechanisms to reliably implement these limits, analysing their impacts (direct and indirect), determining desirable limits for each indicator to ensure compliance with planetary boundaries, and so on.

These limits can vary over time, for example, to smooth out peak usage (i.e., with peak/off-peak hour mechanisms) or, conversely, be fixed at the manufacturing stage (by design). In the case of time-varying limits, issues of flexible use arise, with potential rebound effects.

These limits can also be physical (low-tech) in terms of data volume, number of transistors, lifespan, etc. They can be defined at collective scales (a team, a company, an administration, a region, etc.) or individual scales. Digital sufficiency also raises the question of limiting usefulness and restricting usage, with major and inseparable implications: issues about social

justice and fairness. The social effects of these limitations, whether stemming from regulations, incentives, or self-restraint practices, must be studied to avoid negative consequences (social inequalities, digital divide, etc.) and problematic behaviours (e.g., addictions). Adopting sober behaviours also raises questions about user appropriability and desirability.

Resilience

Finally, in parallel, studies have been conducted around resilience, meaning defining the kind of ICT that would help to cope with disruptive situations. It concerns both the resilience of digital technology itself in facing disruptions (e.g., intermittent electricity, shortages of materials or ICT components, water restrictions) and the resilience of other systems in facing ICT disruptions (e.g., outages, unavailability).

These two resilience directions seem orthogonal to reducing the environmental impacts of ICT. Indeed, the resilience of an ICT system is often characterised as its robustness and fault tolerance, and resource overallocation and redundancy methods are de facto standards to guarantee these two criteria. It is therefore necessary to propose other robustness methods that take planetary boundaries into account. These methods could, for example, explore much more decentralised architectures in the management of large ICT systems (communication networks, cloud infrastructures, etc.).

Foresight studies are a valuable tool for resilience research. Indeed, they allow us to anticipate in the face of uncertainty, and they provide methods for exploring future scenarios (rather than predicting them). These studies enable us to envision the future and, through the study of possible or desirable futures, to identify major trends, weak signals, or potential disruptions. Adapting hardware and software infrastructures to these potential disruptions or shortages remains a largely underexplored area.

The resilience of digital technology itself also raises questions of adaptability, repairability, and conviviality [Illich 1973], as well as issues of conflicting uses, and even user prioritisation in the event of very limited ICT resources or crisis management. Finally, resilience raises the question of the role of ICT in our future with increasingly tangible planetary boundaries and leads to research questions about dedigitalisation of other sectors.

Conclusion

Underlying these four axes is the question of the role of research in this environmental crisis and

the individual and collective responsibility of higher education and research staff. How can we address these systemic challenges that raise ethical questions? What are our narratives about computer science? What kind of ICT do we dream of? What kind of ICT are we inventing? What kind of ICT are we telling in our research, development, teaching, and applications? Will this future ICT be sustainable, respectful of the environment, and of planetary boundaries? Will it contribute to guaranteeing a decent and equitable standard of living for all?

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